

The effect of word of mouth on the international attractiveness of Moroccan international universities: a study focusing on foreign students

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Abstract

The international attractiveness of universities is a subject that arouses the interest of all stakeholders in the sector of higher education in its international dimension, the mobility of students at the international level does not cease to grow , so the number of students in international mobility has increased considerably during the last decade (on average 5.5% per year), Morocco is not escaping this trend, so, for the academic year 2019-2020, in terms of incoming international mobility, more than 25. 000 international students were pursuing their higher education in the various Moroccan training and higher education centers. Indeed, attracting foreign students is not an easy task for universities, so our study intervenes to understand even one mechanism behind this complex but essential process. The purpose of this study is to answer the following question: To what extent does the word of mouth generated by foreign students impact the international attractiveness of Moroccan universities. In other words, we are interested in studying the effect of word of mouth generated by foreign students enrolled in Moroccan universities on the choice of potential foreign students . In order to answer our problem, a survey by questionnaire was carried out with 120 foreign students registered in medicine in the UIASS and the UM6SS. This survey allowed us to validate the hypothesis according to which the positive word of mouth generated by foreign students concerning their university impacts in a positive and significant way the choice of other potential students in the context of the Moroccan private higher education. Indeed, despite the difficulty of measuring "consumer intent," our research validated the positive and significant impact of word of mouth on consumer choice in the higher education sector. Our study was applied to the higher education sector, but we believe that it could be applied to other sectors in order to reach sectors other than higher education.

Keywords: International attractiveness of universities , word of mouth

Résumé :

L'attractivité internationale des universités est un sujet qui suscite l'intérêt de toutes les parties prenantes du secteur de l'enseignement supérieur dans sa dimension internationale, la mobilité des étudiants à l'échelle internationale ne cesse de croître, ainsi le nombre des étudiants en mobilité internationale a considérablement augmenté durant la dernière décennie (en moyenne de 5,5 % par an), le Maroc n'échappe pas à cette tendance, ainsi, au titre de l'année universitaire 2019-2020, en matière de mobilité internationale entrante, plus de 25.000 étudiants internationaux poursuivaient leurs études supérieures dans les différents centres de formations et d'enseignement supérieur marocains. En effet, attirer des étudiants étrangers n'est pas une tâche facile pour les universités, ainsi notre étude intervient pour comprendre ce qui ne serait-ce qu'un mécanisme derrière ce processus complexe mais primordiale. L'objet de la présente étude est de répondre à la problématique suivante : Dans quelle mesure le bouche à oreille engendré par les étudiants étrangers impacte-t-il l'attractivité internationale des universités marocaines. En d'autres termes, nous nous intéressons à l'étude de l'effet du bouche à oreille engendré par des étudiants étrangers inscrits dans des universités marocaines sur le choix d'étudiants étrangers potentiels. Afin de répondre à notre problématique, une enquête par questionnaire a été menée auprès de 120 étudiants étrangers inscrits en filière médecine dans l'UIASS et l'UM6SS, cette enquête nous a permis de valider l'hypothèse selon laquelle le bouche à oreille positif engendré par des étudiants étrangers concernant leur université impacte de manière positive et significative le choix d'autres étudiants potentiels dans le contexte de l'enseignement supérieur privé marocain. En effet malgré la difficulté de mesurer «l'intention du consommateur», notre recherche a permis de valider l'impact positif et significatif du bouche à oreille sur le choix du consommateur dans le domaine de l'enseignement supérieur. Notre étude a été appliquée au secteur de l'enseignement supérieur, la possibilité de l'appliquer à d'autres secteurs nous paraît envisageable pour toucher des secteurs autres que l'enseignement supérieur.

Mots clés : Attractivité internationale des universités, bouche à oreille

Introduction :

In a context of internationalization of higher education , Coates (2005) joins the Anglo-Saxon sphere and highlights the Australian model where students are in search of information to decide on their choice . In the present work, the student's choice is studied through the consumer's choice. Indeed, the consumer choice is not random, previous studies associate it with several factors, one of the main factors is the word of mouth .

The present study focuses on the impact of word of mouth generated by foreign students on the international attractiveness of Moroccan universities. Indeed, this topic represents concerns all stakeholders in the higher éducation sector, mainly managers of higher education institutions to respond to their strategic visions, notably the vision of attracting a maximum number of foreign students and improving the institution's visibility on an international scale. In other words, our research work aims to provide managers of higher education institutions with the elements that will allow them to judge that it is strategically important to act on students' behaviour in order to improve their attractiveness. Thus, the present work proposes to shed light on new theoretical approaches likely to bring improvements in managerial practices in the field of higher education.

In this sense, several studies have been interested in studying the effect of word of mouth on consumer choice, as an example, the studies of (Katz , 1955; Monahan , 1984; Bristor , 1990; Engel, Blackwell and Kegerreis , 1969; Dellarocas 2003; Werbler and Harris , 2008 and Bourgeon and Kruger , 2010; Burzynski and Bayer , 1977; Herr, Kardes and Kim , 1991; Bone , 1995). In this context, we will attempt to answer the following question: To what extent does an international student's communication impact the choice of potential international students? Regarding the approach adopted to collect and analyze the data, we adopted a quantitative approach with foreign students enrolled in the medical field in the UIASS and the UM6SS with the SPSS software.

Our study is structured in three parts, first the Literature review, which explains the International attractiveness of universities, Word of mouth in the context of our study and The influence of word of mouth on consumer behavior , secondly the Methodology in which we present the Operationalization of variables , the study background and sampling and the sample and Data collection and thirdly we will present and discuss our results .

1. Literature review :

1. International attractiveness of universities

The international attractiveness of universities is a reflection of their scientific, educational and cultural influence. Indeed, several researchers in management and social sciences have studied the attractiveness of higher education institutions and student mobility. These studies mainly focus on the capacity of higher education institutions to attract a maximum number of students in several contexts, notably, the training of elites, the transfer of knowledge and the commodification of the higher education sector (Michèle, Grazia, & Anne-Catherine, 2011)) The drainage of foreign students is nowadays a part of the strategic logic of internationalization of higher education institutions .

Moreover, these strategies take shape in different approaches undertaken with the intention of attracting more and more foreign students, with a view to attracting the best students or recruiting students with sufficient financial resources to finance their university studies abroad. From this perspective, Jean-Philippe (2013) compares the attractiveness of higher education institutions to the transfer strategy of soccer players in the sports field. With the internalization of higher education, the competition between higher education institutions goes beyond national borders, higher education institutions must be part of a strategic logic that relies on a competitive advantage that can act directly on the behavior of the student especially concerning the choice of the latter, mainly the international student.

In the field of higher education, "Attractiveness is a power of seduction over students, a power deployed as much by States as by institutions. And this, through specific programs, fame or other modalities and standards of spectacularization and valorization of results as well as reputation of the university institution wishing to internationalize (Elieth & Séverine, 2015) . Moreover, the notion of attractiveness is not sufficiently developed in the contemporary literature on higher education. However, it is directly associated with the notion of territory in economic geography (Dévoué, 2005), which is why we have studied the notion of attractiveness through other constructs, notably that of consumer behavior and student choice.

1.2.The essence of word of mouth in our study:

Word of mouth is not a new concept, it has existed even before researchers began to focus on it. Moreover, Roux (1990) and Stambouli (2002) explain that the word of mouth was imposed through two elements, the first one concerns its influence on the market and the second one concerns the persuasive side that operates on the consumer. As for Voss (1997), he demonstrated

through a study that he had conducted, that 80% of purchasing decisions were determined by the word of mouth or by recommendations .

Many researches have been interested in the study of the word of mouth , but few of them have studied its measurement . Indeed (Harrison-walker , 2001 ; Godes , 2004 ; Goyette , 2007) have studied the measurement of word of mouth . Harrison-walker (2001) identified two dimensions of the word of mouth , "praise" which consists in saying good things about the company and "activity" which consists in the action of making word of mouth (Goyette 2007). In this sense, (Godes 2004) emphasized two other dimensions of word of mouth , "the volume" which reflects the frequency related to the word of mouth communication and the "dispersion".

Indeed, Goyette (2007) completes the Harrison-walker scale by elaborating a scale with 4 dimensions, content, activity, positive polarity and negative polarity (Moulin & Roux, 2008). The conclusions of the studies of (Goyette 2007) note that the dimension "content" is composed of two sub-dimensions, the first "I discuss the prices of the products offered" and "I discuss the quality of the products offered", the second "I discuss the quality of the products offered". The "activity" dimension includes three sub-dimensions: "I have talked about this company more than any other online company", "I have talked about this company more frequently than any other type of company" and finally "I have talked about this company to several individuals". The third dimension which is "positive polarity" or "praise" involves six statements, "I recommend this company", "I talk about the good things about the company", "I strongly recommend people to buy products online from this company", "I said positive things to others most of the time" and finally "I spoke favorably about the company online". Finally, we find the "negative polarity" dimension composed, according to Goyette (2007), of two statements: "I spoke unfavorably about the company" and "I said negative things".

1.3.The influence of the word of mouth on consumer behavior:

Several researchers have been interested in studying the impact of the word of mouth on consumer behavior through the study of purchase intention and consumer choice behavior.

1.3.1. The influence of word of mouth on the purchase intention and on the consumer's choice ::

Today we are witnessing the multiplication of advertising strategies, which is why consumers are no longer able to decide on the final choice of product or service. To do this, the consumer tries to consult the opinions of other consumers in order to make a choice. In this context, the consumer is automatically influenced by the recommendations of others, whether he likes it or

not, his purchase intention and his choice are linked to it. To understand this process, we have reviewed the literature in order to focus on the purchase intention and on the models of purchase behavior associated with the word of mouth .

Indeed, the word of mouth coming from non commercial sources represents according to (Okazaki 2009) one of the most influential means of information communication, while the consumer's decision making process is the result of the information processing process (Filser 1994) . Consumer behavior is determined by two mechanisms, the first associated with normative influence considered both positive and negative, the second is associated with informative influence occurred when the consumer does not have enough informations to make his choice (dominique 2009) .

Regarding the effect of the word of mouth on the consumer's choice process, Julia (1990) considers it to be "a person-to-person oral communication between a sender and a receiver, who perceives information about a product, brand, or service that he or she considers to be noncommercial" (Dominic 2009). In this sense, Herret et al (1991) explain that commercial information is less influential on the consumer's choice process than information in the context of word of mouth . In this sense, Georges (1984) established a stochastic model comparing the effects of word of mouth communication and commercial communication. Following his study, he concluded that the introduction of a new product on the market is determined by the advertising campaigns and the word of mouth between those who have already tried the product and those who have not yet tried it.

In this sense, Cooper-Martin (1992) explains that the choice of an experiential product is associated with an experiential source of information. To define the effect of the word of mouth on consumer choice, Brown and Peter (1987) proposed a social view of the latter with reference to two elements, first the level of the relationship between the senders and receivers and secondly , the intensity of the links between the senders and receivers of the word of mouth communication.

Within this framework, (Julia 1990) presented the consequences of word of mouth as follows, Firstly the effect of word of mouth impacts all stages of the consumer choice process, secondly the effect of word of mouth is the consequence of a process of multiple dyads, thirdly the effect of word of mouth gives rise to a process of retranscription.

The literature on the effect of the word of mouth on consumer choice has shed light on a concept that is closely related to this relationship. This is the concept of the "opinion leader". According

to Flynn, Ronald and Goldsmith (1996) , the concept of opinion leader is the result of a fact, the messages coming from the media sources do not reach the consumer directly, but touch him via an intermediary, this intermediary is the opinion leader, moreover this concept appeared for the first time following the works of (Lazarfeld, Berelson, Gaudet 1940). According to these authors, the opinion leader is "a person who, through daily personal contact, regularly influences the opinion and decision of others on one or more subjects" (Bergeron and Ricard 2003). Referring to the effects of the word of mouth , we find that word of mouth impacts consumer choice more than the media.

In this context, Katz and Lazarfeld (1955) studied the impact of word of mouth on consumer choice in four sectors by comparing this impact with that of the mass media. Their study concluded that word of mouth communication has a greater impact on consumer choice than commercial communication. Indeed, Mckinsey and Company conducted a study that concluded that 67% of consumer purchases are based on personal information sources (Taylor 2003). In another study conducted by the same firm, 60% of respondents consider the word of mouth to be the most important source of influence in making their choices (Engel, Blackwell and Kegerreis 1969).

1.3.2. The impact of electronic word of mouth on consumer choice and purchase intention:

Moez and Faouzia's (2015) investigated the impact of electronic word of mouth on consumer behavior, including brand image, attitude, and purchase intention in the banking sector. The survey was conducted through the administration of 180 questionnaires to a recognized bank. The results concluded that the electronic word of mouth had an impact on purchase intention. Nowadays, the Internet is increasingly becoming a very powerful channel in the dissemination of word of mouth (Youn & Kuntaraporn, 2006) . According to Dellarocas (2003), the internet is a way to share their opinions and experiences about a product or service, which facilitates other people to judge the product or service before making a decision based on other people's experience. Referring to a survey by the Opinion Research Corporation (2010), Werbler and Harris (2008) explains that the results concluded that (61%) of the respondents answered that they consulted reviews on the internet to decide on the purchase of a product or service.

In this sense, online reviews are considered by several researchers to be a very determining source of consumers' purchase intention (Bickart and Schindler , 2001 ; Goldenberg 2001 ; Duan and Whinston , 2008 ; Wooders , 2006 ; Park and Lee , 2009 and Xiaofen , 2009).

Moreover, (Bickart and Schindler (2001)) explain this by two reasons, firstly because other people's opinions are considered by consumers as very credible and secondly, it is very normal for consumers to identify with other consumers.

Several researchers have empirically tested the effect of electronic word of mouth on the purchase intention of other consumers (Lee and Thadani , 2009 and Zhang, Craciuna and Shin , 2010). The study of Bourgeon and Kruger (2010) sheds light on the effect of word of mouth on the choice process of the movie viewer, the research tries to shed light on the link between word of mouth and the decision making process of the movie viewer. Indeed, the study was conducted through a questionnaire administered to a convenience sample of 331 people with the aim of measuring first the intensity of the word of mouth effect and then the direction of the word of mouth effect .

In this framework , Ezzahi and Jazi (2018) conducted a netnographic study on groups in social networks and mainly Facebook , the study mainly concerns products purchased via websites in an international context . In this regard, the study of Ben Mbarek and Trabelssi (2018) has shed light on the variable "perceived quality of the brand" as a determinant of the purchase intention, these researchers have examined the effect of electronic word of mouth on the purchase intention in the world of cinema, for this purpose, they conducted a qualitative study with interviews, to be completed with a quantitative study through a questionnaire to be filled out online, their study concluded that the electronic word of mouth impacts in a positive and significant way the purchase intention of the consumer in the cinema field.

2. Methodology

2.1. Operationalization of variables

The operationalization of the variables is a crucial step in our research, the word of mouth is measured in terms of recommendation intention and recommendation, in this part we referred to the studies of Bigne et al. (2005); Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1985); Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988); Zeithaml, Berry, and Parasuraman (1996) and Zeithaml and Bitner (1996). We used 4 items. The measurement scales used in the questionnaire are the five-point "Likert" type where "1" means "strongly agree", "5" means "strongly disagree". The table below represents a summary of the measurement scales .

Table 1: Summary of word of mouth Measurement Scales

The word of mouth
Je recommanderai l'université que j'ai choisie en tant qu'université de qualité à toute personne qui me demandera conseil
Si un jour, une discussion m'amène à parler des choix des universités, je parlerai favorablement de mon université
J'encouragerai mes amis et mes relations à faire des études dans l'université que j'ai choisi
Je dirai des choses positives à mon entourage au sujet de mon université

Source : established by us

To measure consumer choice, we used three items with a five-point Likert-type scale where "1" means "strongly agree" and "5" means "strongly disagree". In this context, we reviewed empirical studies to draw inspiration from them, but we found that the literature is poor on the subject, which led us to propose our own items. The table below shows a summary of the measurement scales for the consumer choice variable.

Table 2: Summary of consumer choice measurement scales

Consumer choice
I influenced others to choose my university
People I recommended the university to will enroll in the future
All the people I recommended the university have enrolled

Source : established by us

2.2. Study background and sampling :

Our study applies to the field of higher education in Morocco, the student represents our main object of research, so we wanted to choose a sample fairly representative of the population. The data collection was conducted in a direct way, we visited the sites selected to carry out the study, and then we administered the questionnaires to students who correspond to the characteristics of our sample. Indeed, the choice of the mode of collection implies a presence of our part on the ground and also more a good reactivity on behalf of the students. To this end, we conducted our study with foreign students enrolled in the medicine program at two Moroccan international universities specializing in the health sciences.

The choice of the research field is mainly related to the context that the researcher seeks to study. , we have conducted our study in international universities in Morocco, especially private medical schools in Morocco. Indeed, in Morocco, as of 2014, medical studies are no longer provided only by faculties attached to public universities, it is moreover the year 2014 that witnessed the creation of the first two private faculties of medicine linked to Moroccan university hospital centers. In Morocco, as in all countries in the world, medical studies are quite long studies combining theoretical and practical training, these studies are mainly composed of three cycles, and the overall duration of training generally varies from 8 years to 13 years. Indeed, we have chosen to conduct our research in international universities specialized in the field of health, especially in the faculties of medicine that are attached to them .

Moreover, there are three faculties in Morocco that meet our criteria for choosing the target population, namely, medical faculties, private faculties and faculties of international universities , the Abulcasis Faculty of Medicine attached to the Abulcasis International University of Health Sciences (UIASS), the Faculty of Medicine attached to the Mohammed VI University of Health Sciences (UM6SS), and finally the private faculty of medicine in Marrakech attached to the Private University of Marrakech (UPM).

After reflection, we decided to conduct the study in two of these faculties, namely, the Faculty of Medicine of Rabat and the Faculty of Medicine of Casablanca. This choice of area is easily justified, because these two faculties were created in 2014, so the students enrolled there better respond to our problem, while the recently enrolled students (Private Faculty of Medicine of Marrakech - created in 2018) are not yet able to propose elements of responses to our problem, so their participation could bias our study.

2.3.The questionnaire and data collection :

We wanted to interview foreign students enrolled in the medical field. To do this, we selected our sample using the reasoned choice method. Indeed, a sample composed by a reasoned choice refers to theoretical criteria determined by the researcher's judgment (Thietard 2007). We we have chosen as criteria the field of study and the nationality, for the field of study we retained the medical field of study and for the nationality, we retained any foreign nationality presenting itself to us. Indeed, it was essential for us to have a relevant sample with reference to the structure of our target population. We we have chosen a convenience sample of 130 students who responded to our questionnaire.

Our questionnaire was structured as follows:

Table 3: The structure of our questionnaire

Content	Interest of the content	Number of questions	Types of measurement scales
General information on the choice of higher education institutions	Inquire about: Student financial aid, level of effort in processing the application, overall satisfaction level, criteria for choosing , accessibility of information prior to enrollment...	8	Nominal scale
General information about the word of mouth	Know : The content of the word of mouth communication The volume of the word of mouth The dispersion of the word of mouth The catalyst The transmission	6	Nominal scale
Consumer Choice and word of mouth	The impact of the word of mouth on consumer choice	1	Likert scale
Socio-demographic variables	Gender, age, nationality, parents' occupation, type of secondary school attended, year of enrollment	7	Nominal scale

Source : established by us

In the present study, we adopt a Likert scale, we made this choice because first of all this scale is easy and practical. Regarding the number of categories of the scale, the literature recommends working with a number of points up to 7 points. The number of points depends on the

researcher's objective and the precision of the information sought. This choice facilitated the administration of the questionnaire and allowed us to use structural equation modelling, which requires continuity the data and a scale with a minimum of five points. Here are the selected adjectives and the order:

Totally agree	agree	Neither in disagreement nor in agreement	Disagree	Totally disagree
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The data collection was extended for a period of three months (December, January and February 2019/2020). 130 questionnaires were distributed, following which we obtained 120 questionnaires, the analysis of the results was conducted through the SPSS software.

3. Results and discussions:

3.1.Factor analysis with the Varimax rotation :

According to (Evard & Pras, 2003), the factorial analysis of the multivariate data is the most used method because of the advantages associated to it, namely the advantage of explaining the relations between the variables by reducing the initial number of these variables in order to test the unidimensionality of the measurement scale. In fact, in this study we have adopted ACP in order to design and refine the measurement instruments of our questionnaire. This analysis will allow us to condense the existing information in a rather large number of items into a smaller set of items while ensuring a logical and correct loss of information.

For each of our variables, we have a scale highlighted following the elements emerging from the ACP. From this point of view, we proceeded to the verification of the stability of the scale over time and we also verify if the scale allows to evaluate the predefined construct. Then we adopted an internal consistency analysis through the use of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient .

Although Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is sensitive to the sample size and the number of items, the results are very satisfactory, which implies that the items we kept after the application of the factorial analysis allow us to better understand our research axes. Indeed, our results conclude that the value of the coefficient exceeds 0.77 for the majority of the variables studied, an excellent result because it exceeds the limit of 0.6, the value adopted by the scientific community.

Following these results, we note that the internal consistency of the measurement items is confirmed, the axes that we have set up are retained to be used for the rest of the analysis. Indeed, these results allow us to have new scales of measures and to integrate the existing measures to the specificity of our study.

3.2. Analysis of the kaiser-meyer-olkin (kmo) index and bartlett sphericity test:

The purpose of analyzing the KMO Index and Bartlett's Sphericity Test is to measure the adequacy of the sampling and whether the matrix is an identity matrix.

The table below represents the results of the KMO Index and Bartlett's Sphericity Test following a factor analysis for the validation of the measurement items.

Tableau 4 : Result of the analysis of the KMO index and Bartlett's sphericity test

Variable	Indice KMO et test de Bartlett		
Word of mouth	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality.		,829
	Bartlett's sphericity test	Khi-deux approx.	429,293
		ddl	6
		Signification	,000
Students' choice	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for measuring sampling quality.		,659
	Bartlett's sphericity test	Khi-deux approx.	103,978
		ddl	3
		Signification	,000

The KMO index measures the quality of the sample. A value below 0.6 indicates that we have a poor correlation between items. If it is less than 0.5, the sample should be revised.

For the variable "word of mouth", the KMO index is equal to 0.829 which is an excellent result. This indicates that the correlations between the items of the variable "word of mouth" are of good quality. The result of Bartlett's sphericity test for the variable "word of mouth" is significant ($p < 0.05$). We can therefore conclude that the correlations of the items of this variable are not all equal to zero (We do not have an identity matrix).

For the variable "Student Choice", the KMO index is equal to 0.659 , which is an excellent result. This tells us that the correlations between the items of the variable "Student Choice" are of good quality. The result of Bartlett's sphericity test for the variable "Student Choice" is

significant ($p < 0.05$). We can therefore conclude that the correlations of the items of this variable are not all equal to zero (We do not have an identity matrix).

The result of the Bartlett's sphericity test is significant for all of our variables. The correlations obtained are therefore not all equal to zero, which allows us to continue with the correlation and normality tests of the variables that make up our research model.

3.3. Analysis of the correlation :

The correlation analysis is used to test if there are relationships between two random variables, it also gives the possibility of highlighting the intensity of the link between two variables, because the correlation coefficient is between -1 and 1.

On the other hand, when the correlation coefficient approaches -1, the two variables studied vary in two opposite directions. On the other hand, when the correlation coefficient approaches 0, the two variables are considered to be interdependent on each other. In order to evaluate the correlation coefficient, it must be significant (the p-value must be smaller than 0.05). The correlation coefficient informs the researcher about the direction of the existing relationship between the two variables and the intensity of the relationship between them.

3.4. Analysis of the correlation between word of mouth and student choice

The relationship between the Word of Mouth variable and the Student Choice variable is positive and significant correlation ($R= 0.462$; $p\text{-value}= 0.000$), when the Word of Mouth variable increases, the Student Choice variable also increases.

Our results confirm the positive correlation between word of mouth and consumer choice in the higher education sector , these results have been confirmed by other researchers in other settings. (The discussion will shed light on the comparison of our results with researchers who have studied the same impact).

The analysis of the nature of the correlations linking the different variables cannot confirm or deny the research hypotheses on its own.

Representation of consumer choice measurement scales

The table below provides a description of foreign students responses regarding the influence of the students surveyed on the choice of their higher education institution .

Item 1: I have influenced others to choose my university		
		Pourcentage
Valide	I agree	40,8
	Neither disagree nor agree	22,5
	Disagree	11,7
	Not at all in agreement	10,0
	Totally agree	15,0
	Total	100,0

The table below provides a description of the responses of foreign students regarding student feedback following the recommendation of their higher education institution.

Item 2: People to whom I have recommended the university will enroll later		
		Pourcentage
Valide	I agree	24,2
	Neither disagree nor agree	38,3
	Disagree	13,3
	Not at all in agreement	15,8
	Totally agree	8,3
	Total	100,0

The table below provides a description of the responses of foreign students regarding student enrollment following the recommendation of their higher education institution .

Item 3: All the people to whom I recommended the university, enrolled there		
		Pourcentage
Valide	I agree	4,2
	Neither disagree nor agree	47,5
	Disagree	24,2
	Not at all in agreement	21,7
	Totally agree	2,5
	Total	100,0

Based on the students' responses to the "consumer choice" variable, we find that on the first item, more than 50% of the students surveyed either agreed or strongly agreed that they influenced others to choose the same university.

Regarding the second item, we found that almost 32% of the students surveyed agreed or strongly agreed that people to whom they recommended the university would enroll in the future.

Finally, concerning the last item, we note that the students' answers were rather unfavorable since only 4.2% of students confirmed that all the people they recommended the university to enrolled , have enrolled .

We note that following the purification of the scales, all the items of this variable were kept. Indeed this part allowed us to study the impact of the word of mouth on consumer choice in our context.

3.5. Results of the structural equation modeling :

Structural equation models allow researchers to identify, understand, guide and evaluate the relationships between variables, these models also allow for the existence of measurement errors in the estimation of latent variable indicators.

	Word of mouth	Students choice
Rho of convergent validity	0,8250	0,6909
R ² _{ij} Word of mouth	1,0000	0,2134
R ² _{ij} Students choice	0,2134	1,0000
Convergent Validity	Validée	Validée
Discriminant Validity	Validée	Validée

According to the table above, we were able to have convergent validity and discriminant validity for the two variables studied namely word of mouth and student choice. This validates the results of the ACP factorization with Varimax rotation. We now move on to the next step.

3.6. Analysis of parameter estimates and validation of assumptions

We now turn to the analysis of the estimation of the parameters of the causal model in order to study the significance of the links and to validate our hypothesis. The following table presents the results of the Student's T test and the significance.

Table 5 : Causality results and validation of research hypotheses

				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Choix des étudiants	<---	Bouche à oreille		0,49	0,091	5,398	***	Accepté

The "Word of Mouth" variable has a positive and significant impact on the "Student Choice" variable (R= 0.490; Student's T= 5.398; p-value= 0.000) (Impact accepted). When the "Word of Mouth" variable increases, the "Student Choice" variable also increases.

The results of our structural equation model are very satisfactory, we accept the results and present the validation of our hypothesis.

3.7. Discussion of the results :

Table 6: Summary of the results of the validation of our hypotheses

HYPOTHESE	VALIDATION
THE WORD OF MOUTH POSITIVELY INFLUENCES THE CHOICE OF FOREIGN STUDENTS	ACCEPTED

SOURCE : established by us

Regarding the impact of the word of mouth on consumer choice, our results confirmed the hypothesis that the word of mouth influences the choice of a higher education institution . Indeed, many researchers have tried to test Katz's (1955) thesis according to which the word of mouth influences the purchase decision. However, this impact has not been tested in the context of higher education. In this sense, Paul et al.(1991) agreed with our results by confirming that commercial information is less influential on the consumer choice process than word of mouth. In this sense, the study of Georges (1984) concluded that the introduction of a new product on the market is determined by advertising campaigns and the word of mouth between those who have already tried the product and those who have not yet tried it. Other authors have affirmed that the word of mouth influences the choice of the consumer, thus, Julia (1990) concluded that the word of mouth impacts all the stages of the process of the consumer choice , as for Katz and Lazarfeld (1955), they studied the impact of the word of mouth on the choice of the consumer in four sectors by comparing this impact with that of the mass media, their study concluded that the communication word of mouth impacts more the choice of the consumer compared to the communication of commercial nature. Furthermore, Mckinsey and Company concluded that 67% of consumer purchases are based on personal information sources. In another study by the

same firm, 60% of respondents considered the word of mouth to be the most important source of influence in making their choices (Engel, Blackwell and Kegerreis 1969).

In another perspective, the study of Dellarocas (2003) concluded that the Internet is a way to share their opinions and experiences about a product or service, which facilitates other people to judge the product or service before making a decision based on the experience of others. A survey by Opinion Research Corporation (2010) found that 61% of respondents said they consulted reviews on the Internet when deciding to purchase a product or service. The study by Bourgeon & Kruger (2010) sheds light on the positive effect of word of mouth on the moviegoer's choice process, thus word of mouth impacts consumer choice in the movie world. The literature review is very rich in proving the positive impact of word of mouth on consumer choice, but this impact has not been tested in the field of higher education .

Conclusion :

Our study presents several contributions, limits and perspectives.

Regarding the contributions of our study, the literature allows us to note that in the field of word of mouth (mainly concerning the measurement of it), few researchers are interested in it. In the field of higher education we have not found any study that deals with the impact of the word of mouth on consumer choice, so our research has validated the positive and significant impact of the word of mouth on consumer choice in the field of higher education. Indeed, this impact has been tested and proven by other researchers in other contexts .

Regarding the limitations of our study, the main limitation of our study is that we focused on consumer intentions and actual behavior, the variable "consumer intention" is difficult to measure. Thus, in measuring the impact of the word of mouth on consumer choice, we focused on the "intention to enroll " instead of focusing on actual behavior, even though several authors have considered intention as a determinant of actual behavior, We consider this aspect of our work to be a significant limitation. Another limitation is that the number of statements measuring the impact of the word of mouth on the choice of potential students, and the items associated with them, were developed by us, since the literature review did not yield any results. Another methodological limitation of the research is the lack of empirical validation of the positive impact of the word of mouth on consumer choice in the higher education sector to compare with our results .

Considering the discussion of our results and the limitations of this study, we envision new avenues of future research to enrich this study :

- Our research has been applied to the higher education sector, the possibility of applying it to other sectors seems conceivable in order to reach other .
- From a methodological point of view, we believe that it would be interesting to continue our research on three different faculties to see if the change in course of study would lead to other results.
- Following our study, we found that the word of mouth is important in the choice of the students interviewed, mainly the traditional word of mouth , we think it would be interesting to conduct a study to understand why the electronic word of mouth is not significantly influential on the choice of foreign students , this will allow us to define the determinants leading to generate an electronic word of mouth.

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